

EVALUATION OF STRAIN ENERGY RELEASE RATES OF MIXED-MODE FRACTURE SPECIMEN FOR LAMINATED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A modified ENF specimen for the mixed-mode fracture test was analyzed by the finite element method. The analysis was performed to calculate strain energy release rates and to compare the results with those obtained by the beam theory analysis. For various thickness ratios of the modified ENF specimen, the variation of G_I/G_T values by the finite element analysis showed some discrepancy with the result by the beam theory analysis. Present results show that the mode partitioning by the beam theory analysis does not hold good for the specimen with different thickness of upper and lower arms.

Keywords : Laminated composite, Mixed-mode, Mode partitioning, Strain energy release rate

1. INTRODUCTION

Delamination is one of the predominant failure modes in laminated composites. The delamination of laminated composites initiates and grows mostly under the combined modes except the artificial load condition for pure mode. The resistance of laminated composites to the delamination growth is evaluated by the interlaminar fracture toughness, and the interlaminar fracture toughness of laminated composites depends on the contribution of mode I to total strain energy release rate. Therefore, in order to understand the behavior of laminated composites with delamination, not only pure mode I and mode II but also mixed-mode interlaminar fracture toughness should be evaluated.

Double cantilever beam (DCB) and end notched flexure (ENF) specimen have been widely used for the pure mode I and mode II interlaminar fracture toughness, respectively [1,2]. Several types of specimens have been discussed to evaluate mixed-mode interlaminar fracture toughness in the literature [3-5]. Among the specimens, mixed-mode flexure(MMF) specimen, proposed by Russell and Street [5], is similar to the ENF specimen except that the load is applied to the upper arm of the delaminated region. From experimental point of view it is not convenient to apply the loading to the MMF specimen due to the use of loading block. Recently, the modified ENF specimen was proposed by Yoon and Hong [6]. This specimen is simply loaded under three-point bending to induce mixed-mode deformation near the delamination tip. The variation of contribution of mode I to total strain energy release rate can be achieved by varying the location of delamination in the direction of thickness. They calculated the strain energy release rates by

beam theory analysis proposed by Williams [7]. In the beam theory analysis, strain energy release rates were calculated from shear forces and bending moments applied to upper and lower arm of the specimen.

In the present work, the beam theory analysis was briefly reviewed. The validity of mode partitioning by the beam theory analysis was examined by finite element method. The finite element analysis of the modified ENF specimen was performed to obtain mode I and mode II strain energy release rates. Results of the beam theory analysis was compared with those by the finite element analysis.

2. BEAM THEORY ANALYSIS

Let us consider a free body diagram near crack tip of a typical beam-type specimen shown in Figure 1. Based on the linear fracture mechanics, total strain energy release rate G_T was presented in Ref. [7].

$$G_T = \frac{I}{16bE_1I} \left\{ \frac{M_1^2}{\xi^3} + \frac{M_2^2}{(1-\xi)^3} - (M_1 + M_2)^2 \right\} + \frac{3}{10bG_{13}A} \left\{ \frac{Q_1^2}{\xi} + \frac{Q_2^2}{(1-\xi)} - (Q_1 + Q_2)^2 \right\} \quad (1)$$

where $I=bh^3/12$, $A=bh$, and $\xi=h_1/2h$. In Equation (1), M_1 and Q_1 are bending moment and shear force respectively applied at the upper section OD in Figure 1. And M_2 and Q_2 are defined similarly at the lower section AO.

For mode partitioning, the bending moments and shear forces were represented by superposition of mode I and mode II components [7].

$$M_1 = -M_I + M_{II}, \quad M_2 = M_I + \psi M_{II} \quad (2a)$$

$$Q_1 = -Q_I + Q_{II}, \quad Q_2 = Q_I + \left(\frac{1-\xi}{\xi} \right) Q_{II} \quad (2b)$$

where $\psi = (1-\xi)^3/\xi^3$. Substituting M_1 , M_2 , Q_1 , and Q_2 into Equation (1), G_T was expressed in the simple algebraic summation without cross product of mode I and mode II components.

$$G_T = G_I + G_{II} \quad (3)$$

where,

$$G_I = \frac{I}{16} \frac{M_I^2}{bE_1I} \frac{1+\psi}{(1-\xi)^3} + \frac{3}{10} \frac{Q_I^2}{bG_{13}A} \left\{ \frac{1}{\xi} + \frac{1}{1-\xi} \right\} \quad (4a)$$

$$G_{II} = \frac{3}{16} \frac{M_{II}^2}{bE_1I} \frac{(1-\xi)}{\xi^2} (1+\psi) \quad (4b)$$

Therefore, mode I and mode II strain energy release rates, G_I and G_{II} , can be easily calculated from bending moments and shear forces applied to each arm in the delaminated region.

For the modified ENF specimen shown in Figure 2(a), the bending moments and shear forces in Equations (2a) and (2b) are $M_1 = -Pa/2$, $Q_1 = P/2$, and $M_2 = Q_2 = 0$.

Table 1. Material properties used in the present analysis.

Graphite/epoxy	$E_1=135$ (GPa)	$E_2=11.0$ (GPa)	$G_{12}=4.82$ (GPa)	$\nu_{12}=0.31$	$\nu_{23}=0.52$
Isotropic	$E=73$ (GPa)	$\nu=0.3$			

3. UNBALANCED DCB SPECIMEN

Based on the mode partitioning by the beam theory analysis, mode II does not contribute to total strain energy release rate of DCB specimen with arms of different thickness (hereafter referred as 'unbalanced DCB') under pure bending moments shown in Figure 2(b). However, geometry of the unbalanced DCB specimen is not symmetric about crack plane so that contribution of mode II may be involved. Therefore, it is necessary to examine the validity of the beam theory analysis for beam-type specimen.

For the simplicity without the loss of generality, let us consider only Equation (2a), for pure bending case. This equation indicates that pure mode I is induced by applying the same magnitude and opposite sense of moment to the upper and lower arms irrespective of the thickness ratio ξ . The deformation near the crack tip of the DCB specimen loaded by the same magnitude and opposite sense of moment was reported to be pure mode I irrespective of thickness ratio in Tada [8]. The condition for the mode I in Equation (2a) is the same as the result of Tada. However, not only loading condition but also the geometry should be symmetry about the crack plane in order to produce pure mode I deformation near the crack tip. Therefore, the unbalanced DCB specimen, whose geometry is not symmetry about crack plane, might produce mixed-mode deformation near the crack tip under the pure bending moment.

Finite element analysis of the DCB specimen with various thickness ratios under pure bending moment was performed to calculate strain energy release rates. The strain energy release rates were calculated by the virtual crack closure (VCC) method [9]. Isotropic materials in Table 1 was considered for the finite element analysis. A typical finite element model of unbalanced DCB specimen consists of 1110 isoparametric 8 node elements for the case of $\xi=0.6$. For numerical computation, a , b , and $2h$ in Figure 2(b) were taken to be 35mm, 25mm, and 5mm, respectively.

When thickness of the upper and lower arms of the specimen is not identical, shear stress is induced along crack plane near crack tip as shown in Figure 3. This indicates that mode II contributes to G_T in the unbalanced DCB specimen. The mixed-mode ratio G_I/G_T of the DCB specimen with thickness ratio ξ is shown in Figure 4. As the difference between thickness of the upper and lower arms becomes larger, the mode II contributes to G_T largely. This contribution of mode II may be induced by asymmetric geometry about crack plane. Therefore, Equation (2a) for mode partitioning is valid only for the beam-type specimen with identical thickness of the upper and lower arms.

4. MODIFIED ENF SPECIMEN

4.1. Specimen Configuration and Materials

The modified ENF specimen shown in Figure 2(a) is a 40-ply laminate with a delamination at one end. The lower arm in the delaminated region is partially cut off so that mixed-mode deformation is produced near crack tip of the specimen loaded under three-point bending. In the Figure 2(a), a is the delamination length, L is the specimen half - span, $2h$ is the total thickness, h_1 is the thickness of upper arm in the delaminated region. Thickness ratio ξ is defined by the ratio of thickness of upper arm to total thickness of the specimen. The total thickness $2h$ is taken equal to 5mm which is nominal thickness of a 40-ply composite laminate, L and a are 50mm and 35mm, respectively, and width b of the specimen is 25mm. The specimen is simply-supported at two ends

and a load P is applied at the mid-span.

Two material systems, isotropic and graphite/epoxy composite material, for the modified ENF specimen were considered in the present analysis. Material properties used in this analysis are given in Table 1.

4.2. Finite Element Analysis

Two-dimensional plane strain analysis of the modified ENF specimen was performed because width of the specimen is large in comparison with the thickness. ANSYS code was utilized with eight-noded quadrilateral elements. In order to express drastic change of stress near crack tip, very fine mesh was used in the vicinity of crack tip with square element around crack tip. Typical finite element mesh for the specimen of $\xi = 0.7$ is shown in Figure 5(a) and fine mesh near crack tip of the model is shown in Figure 5(b). This model consists of 1331 elements and 4226 nodes. The displacement in the y -direction at the nodes corresponding to the two supporting points is constrained, and the displacement in the x -direction at one node is constrained for the prevention of rigid body motion.

G_I and G_{II} were calculated by VCC method and extrapolation(EP) method. G_I and G_{II} by VCC method were calculate from nodal forces around the crack tip and relative displacement between crack faces. G_I and G_{II} by EP method were calculated from the relation between strain energy release rates and the stress intensity factors (K_I and K_{II}) which could be calculated from the relative displacements of crack faces [9]. The quarter-point element for singularity was used to obtain K_I and K_{II} by EP method in this study.

4.3. Numerical Results

Finite element analysis for the specimen of $\xi = 0.3-0.7$ was performed to compare strain energy release rates by the beam theory analysis. Results for the case of $\xi = 0.3, 0.5,$ and 0.7 were summarized in Table 2. As shown in Table 2, results by VCC method were agreed well with those by EP method, however G_I/G_T value by the beam theory analysis is quite different from the value by the finite element analysis for the case of $\xi = 0.3$ and 0.7 .

The G_T/P^2 of the specimen with various thickness ratios is shown in Figure 6, where dashed and solid lines denote results by the beam theory and finite element analysis, respectively. As shown in Figure 6, G_T by the beam theory analysis shows good agreement with the value by the finite element analysis

Figure 7 shows that mixed-mode ratio G_I/G_T by the beam theory analysis is quite different from the result by finite element analysis for the modified ENF specimen. However, results by the beam theory and finite element analysis agree well each other for the case of $\xi = 0.5$. As for the modified ENF specimen with the thickness ratios from 0.3 to 0.7, G_I/G_T values by finite element analysis varied from 0.64 to 0.54 for graphite/epoxy. The variation of G_I/G_T values is very narrower than that by beam theory analysis.

Table 2. Strain energy release rates of the modified ENF specimen for graphite/epoxy.

ξ	No. of Elem.	$G_T/P^2 (\times 10^4), [N m]^{-1}$			$(G_I/G_T), (\%)$		
		EP	VCC	beam theory	EP	VCC	beam theory
0.3	1303	70.57	70.92	62.8	64.5	64.4	95.3
0.5	1325	14.48	14.55	12.3	61.0	60.8	57.5
0.7	1331	3.99	4.02	3.37	54.1	53.8	12.2

5. DISCUSSION

Based on the present results, the Equation (2a) for the superposition of bending moment should be corrected as follows ;

$$M_1 = -M_I + M_{II} \quad (5a)$$

$$M_2 = \alpha M_I + \psi M_{II} \quad (5b)$$

where $\alpha=1.0$ at $\xi=0.5$ and α is unknown value otherwise.

The condition for mode I in Equations (5a) and (5b) states that opposite sense and equal magnitude of bending moments induce pure mode I only for the specimen with the same thickness of the upper and lower arms (i.e. $\alpha=1.0$ at $\xi=0.5$ and α is unknown value at $\xi \neq 0.5$).

Substituting Equations (5a) and (5b) instead of Equation (2a) into Equation (1), G_T can be expressed for the case of no shear forces as follows ;

$$\begin{aligned} G_T = \frac{1}{16bE_1I} & \left[M_I^2 \left\{ \frac{1}{\xi^3} + \frac{\alpha^2}{(1-\xi)^3} - (\alpha-1)^2 \right\} \right. \\ & + M_{II}^2 \left\{ \frac{1}{\xi^3} + \frac{\psi^2}{(1-\xi)^3} - (1+\psi)^2 \right\} \\ & \left. + M_I M_{II} \left\{ -\frac{2}{\xi^3} + \frac{2\alpha\psi}{(1-\xi)^3} - 2(\alpha-1)(\psi+1) \right\} \right] \quad (6) \end{aligned}$$

In Equation (6), G_T has a term of cross product mode I and mode II so that G_T can not be decomposed in this manner. However, when the thickness ratio ξ is 0.5, i.e. $\alpha=1.0$, the last cross product term of Equation (6) becomes zero. Therefore, mode partitioning by the beam theory is valid only at $\xi=0.5$. From this result we could explain the reason why the G_I/G_T values by the beam theory analysis are different from those by the finite element analysis for the thickness ratios from $\xi=0.3$ to $\xi=0.7$ except $\xi=0.5$ shown in Figure 7.

6. CONCLUSION

The validity of mode partitioning of the beam theory analysis was examined by analyzing DCB specimen with various thickness ratios. Finite element analysis was performed to evaluate strain energy release rates of the modified ENF specimen with various thickness ratios. Mode II as well as mode I contributed to G_T for the unbalanced DCB specimen. Therefore, mode partitioning by the beam theory analysis is only valid for the beam-type specimen with identical thickness of the upper and lower arms. As for the modified ENF specimen for the thickness ratios from 0.3 to 0.7, G_I/G_T values by finite element analysis varied from 0.64 to 0.54 for graphite/epoxy. This variation of G_I/G_T values is quite different from result by the beam theory analysis. Mode partitioning by the beam theory analysis does not hold good for the modified ENF specimen with different thickness of the upper and lower arms. However, total strain energy release rate by the beam theory analysis is adequate.

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Figure 1. Bending moments and shear forces near crack tip.

Figure 2. Configuration of specimens and loading.

Figure 3. Distribution of shear stress along crack plane of DCB specimen with various thickness ratios under $M=10^{-3}$ N-m.

Figure 4. Contribution of mode I to total strain energy release rate of DCB specimen with various thickness ratios.

Y coordinates are magnified by 3

(a) Mesh and boundary condition

(b) Fine mesh near crack tip

Figure 5. Finite element model of modified ENF specimen ($\xi=0.7$).

Figure 6. Total strain energy release rate for modified ENF specimen with various thickness ratios.

Figure 7. The contribution of mode I to total strain energy release rate with thickness ratio.